

Situational Leadership Practices in School: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The importance of situational leadership practices in schools is interesting to study. The purpose of this literature review is to analyze situational leadership practices in schools. The articles used in this literature review are articles obtained using the "Google Scholar" database by entering the keyword "situational leadership". There are several literature reviews on situational leadership in schools that were found. Based on the results of literature studies from various countries in the world, it was found that situational leadership style can develop work motivation, improve teacher performance and can increase teacher commitment to the organization.

KEYWORDS: Leadership, Principal, Situational

INTRODUCTION

The industrial revolution 4.0 is an era marked by the rapid development of science and technology (IPTEK). The industrial revolution 4.0 makes the era change so fast that the education system must be able to transform or keep up with the times. Therefore the emphasis on the quality of school leaders is one of the key changes to mobilize educational transformation (Blase & Blase, 1999). Education is one component that carries out a strategic path for national development. Leaders are the main key to the progress of an organization, because leaders are determinants, managers, controllers to direct organizational goals. In directing his subordinates, a leader must have superiority over the people he leads.

The principal as a leader, must always adjust his leadership style according to the demands and changes that occur. The principal must be able to adapt to any conditions and situations that occur in the educational environment, besides that the principal must also be able to influence his followers to make changes in thinking, behaving and behaving to be able to help carry out the goals that have been set (Karoso & Trihantoyo, 2017). The effectiveness of one's leadership, if a leader is able to combine situations and conditions with behavior patterns or leadership styles. In the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 as leaders, school principals are required to have the ability to utilize digital technology, in carrying out their duties and functions so that they can improve the quality of the educators and educational staff they lead. Principal leaders have a very important role in improving teacher quality based on leadership situations where the principal's leadership style varies depending on the maturity level of his subordinates.

Situational leadership theory is based on task behavior, relationship behavior, follower maturity and effective leader behavior (Johansen 1990). The principal's situational leadership places the teacher as the main component that needs full attention and development. As a leadership concept that focuses on the readiness of followers (teachers), the principal as situational leadership focuses on developing the quality of education and influencing the extra role of teacher behavior. The teacher does his job with enthusiasm and puts all his ability in doing his job. Based on this description, it is necessary to know more about "How Situational Leadership Practices in Schools".

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Principal Leadership

The term leadership comes from the English language, namely "leader" which means leader or lead. Leadership is the way in which a leader influences his subordinates to do something. Many definitions of leadership put forward by experts according to their respective points of view. The following are some definitions of leadership put forward by experts:

Leadership is the process by which an individual influences a group (Northouse, 2016). While the principal's leadership is the ability of the principal to lead, and influence the people he leads to be obedient, respectful, loyal, and able to work together (Usman, 2015). Leaders have a very important role in an organization they lead. The importance of the role of leadership in an organization has become a focus that has attracted the attention of researchers in the field of organizational behavior, stating that the quality of leaders

is often considered the most important factor that determines the success or failure of an organization (Bass & Avolio, 1990). The principal has a role as a leader as well as a manager in the school he leads to determine the success and achievement of the school's vision, mission, and goals (Saputra, 2019). The characteristics, attitudes and behaviors of leadership have been studied for decades, also through direct observation of leaders who are considered successful in their leadership. One of the results of this study that is very useful is the study of Kenneth Blanchard and Paul Hersey. They contributed greatly to complement existing leadership theories with an approach based on leadership situations (Roger & Alvin, 1988).

B. Situational Leadership

The third major contingency approach to leadership is situational leadership theory developed by Paul Hersey and Kenneth H. Blanchard. According to this theory, the most effective leadership style varies according to the maturity of the subordinates (Ruky, 2002). Situational leadership is situational leadership that focuses on followers. From this point of view, to be effective a leader must be able to adapt his style to the demands of changing situations. Situational leadership style is a leadership style that focuses on followers, the followers in question are employees in a company. Situational leadership style is applied by looking at the readiness and maturity of its employees to carry out the work given by the leader (Aisyah & Takdir, 2017). Situational leadership is defined as a leadership style in which a leader manages to adapt his style to suit the situation (Setiawan et al., 2019). There are four situational leadership styles, namely the style of instruction, participation, consultation, and delegation (Thoha, 2015). Situational leadership theory rests on two basic concepts, namely: the level of readiness/maturity of individuals or groups as followers and leadership styles. The situational leadership model assisting managers in diagnosing the demands of their situation has been developed as a result of extensive research. As shown in Figure 1, Situational Leadership is based on the interaction between (1) the amount of direction (task behavior) a leader gives, (2) the amount of socio-emotional support (relationship behavior) a leader provides, and (3) the level of "readiness" that followers exhibit for a particular task, function, activity, or goal that the leader wishes to achieve through an individual or group.

Figure 1. Situational Leadership Model

Situational Leadership focuses on the suitability or readiness of followers. This cycle can be illustrated by a bell-shaped curve superimposed on the four leadership quadrants, as shown in Figure 1.

- 1) The high task/low relationship leader (S1) behavior is referred to as “telling” because this style defines the role of followers and tells them what, how, when, and where to perform various tasks.
- 2) The high task/high relationship (S2) leader's behavior is referred to as “selling” because with this style most of the direction is still given by the leader. Leaders also strive through two-way communication and explanation, leaders can guide their followers in the desired direction.
- 3) The behavior of the high/low task relationship leader (S3) is called “participating” because in this style the leader and followers now share in decision making, but the leader is the facilitator. Participating involves high relationship behavior and low task behavior.

- 4) The behavior of the low/low task relationship leader (S4) is “delegating” to high maturity. People have both ability and motivation, as well as little direction. Followers are allowed to decide how, when, and where to do a job. In Delegating involves low relationship behavior and low task behavior (Hersey et al., 1979).

METHOD

The literature review search process begins with a search engine “Google Scholar” by entering the keyword “situational leadership”. Once identified, there were 37,800 articles related to this theme. The criteria for articles in this study are:

Table 1. Criteria for Inclusion Criteria and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
1. Situational leadership	1. Papers/thesis/thesis/dissertation
2. Principal leadership	2. Company/hospital
3. Articles for the last 5 years	3. College
4. Articles are written in English	4. College Leadership

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following presents the results of a literature study that the author has done. The results obtained are regarding the practice of situational leadership in schools. The literature review that has been carried out by the author is as follows:

Table 2. Situational Leadership Practices in Schools

No	Title	Author and Year	Type of Organization	Country	Method	Sample	Results
1	High School Principals' Situational Leadership and Its Relationship with Teachers' Achievement Motivation	Zohair et al., (2021)	School	Jordan	Qualitative	445 teachers	The results showed that the achievement motivation of high school teachers at Diknas I Amman was high, there was a statistically significant difference in the level of achievement motivation by gender, in favor of women, there is a statistically significant difference in the level of teacher motivation achievement with qualifications, in support of science teachers. and there is a statistically significant difference in the level of achievement motivation of teachers with years of experience, supporting teachers with 5-10 years of experience.

No	Title	Author and Year	Type of Organization	Country	Method	Sample	Results
2	The Effect of Principal Situational Leadership and Teacher Professionalism on Teacher Performance	Ruslan et al., (2020)	School	Indonesia	Quantitative	32 teachers	The results of the study indicate that there is an influence of the principal's situational leadership style on the performance of elementary school teachers in Penuguan; there is an influence of teacher professionalism on the performance of elementary school teachers in Penuguan Regency; and there is an effect of the situational leadership style of the principal and the professionalism of the teacher together on the performance of SD Negeri teachers in Penuguan.
3	The Emergence of Situational Leadership During the COVID-19 Pandemic Is Called New Normal Leadership	Francisco & Nuqui (2020)	School	Philippines	Qualitative	-	The findings reveal that: (1) New Normal leadership is the ability to adapt while remaining strong with one's commitment; (2) It is about being an effective instructional decision maker; (3) A leader who is a good planner, vigilant, and initiator.
4	The effects of situational leadership and self-efficacy on the improvement of teachers' work productivity using correlation analysis and SITOREM	Hidayat et al., (2020)	School	Indonesia	Quantitative	105 civil servants (PNS)	The findings show that there is a positive correlation between situational leadership and teacher work productivity with a correlation coefficient of 0.783, and between self-efficacy and teacher work productivity of 0.782. this, therefore, means these two factors are influential in increasing the productivity of teachers.

No	Title	Author and Year	Type of Organization	Country	Method	Sample	Results
5	Increasing Teacher Commitment to Organizations through Organizational Culture Development and Situational Leadership	Suhardi et al., (2019)	School	Indonesia	Quantitative	113 teachers	The results of the research showed that there was a positive relationship between organizational culture and the teacher's commitment to the organization. Besides, there was a positive relationship between situational leadership and the teacher's commitment to the organization. This shows that the teacher's commitment to the organization can be improved through the development of organizational culture, situational leadership, and from the components of the organizational culture itself.
6	Influence Of Situational Leadership Style On Pupils Performance In Kenya Certificate Of Primary Education In Public Primary Schools In Uriri Sub County, Kenya	Ouma et al., (2018).	School	Kenya	Quantitative	A sample of 190 consists of 162 teachers and 28 principals were selected	This study determined that situational leadership is the most effective leadership style that results in increased academic performance. The results of the study show that there is a strong relationship between situational leadership and academic performance of elementary school students in Uriri sub-district, Migori district.
7	The Influence of Principal's Situational Leadership Style and Teacher's Professionalism on	Suarna et al., (2020)	School	Indonesia	Quantitative	-	The results showed that: 1) there was a significant influence of the situational leadership style principal on the performance of state junior high school teachers in East Prabumulih Regency; 2) there is a significant influence between teacher professionalism on teacher

No	Title	Author and Year	Type of Organization	Country	Method	Sample	Results
	Teacher's Performance						performance in public junior high schools in Prabumulih Timur Regency; and 3) there is a significant effect of the situational leadership style of the principal and the professionalism of the teacher together on the performance of state junior high school teachers in Prabumulih Timur Regency.
8	Principal's Leadership Practices during the COVID 19 Pandemic: An Exploratory Study	Pedroso et al., (2021)	School	Philippines	Qualitative	5 principal's	The findings reveal that school principals employed: 1. Strengths-based Practices; 2. Values-based Practices; and 3. Needs-based Practices. The findings of this study highlighted the need of applying situational leadership practices to strengthen principals' instructional and administrative duties, particularly during times of global crises.
9	Situational Leadership Readiness	Arisman & Prihatin (2021)	School	Indonesia	Qualitative	-	The results showed: 1) The principal has implemented situational leadership, it can be seen from the principal who has played a role as telling, selling, participating, and delegating, 2) The supporting factors for implementing situational leadership are the cooperation of various side in carrying out their duties and the availability of facilities and adequate infrastructure. While the inhibiting factor is that there are some teachers who are difficult to work with,

No	Title	Author and Year	Type of Organization	Country	Method	Sample	Results
							3) The impact of the implementation of situational leadership in improving the school quality got an 'A' accreditation score. The success of this situational leadership depends on the principal's ability to determine an attitude with the readiness of the teachers so that they can create effective cooperation
10	Relationship of Situational Leadership Style of Principal and School Climate to Teacher Integrity PAUD at Gambir Sub-District Central Jakarta	Wanto (2021)	School	Indonesia	Quantitative	63 teachers	The results showed that there was a positive relationship between situational leadership style and school climate with the integrity of early childhood teacher in Gambir District, Central Jakarta.
11	The Social Communication Competence as a Softskill of the School Leadership in Archiplego Region	Ismail et al., (2020)	School	Indonesia	Quantitative	28 teachers	The results showed that there was a positive relationship between the principal's situational leadership style and teacher performance. The principal's situational leadership style is largely determined by the ability of social communication as a soft skill he has. The soft skill of the school principal's social communication results in better teacher performance and influences student academic and nonacademic achievement. Contextually

No	Title	Author and Year	Type of Organization	Country	Method	Sample	Results
12	The Investigation Of Situational Leadership, And Work Motivation On Kindergarten Teacher Performance	Mudiyantun, Y. (2019)	School	Indonesia	Quantitative	103 teachers	and situationally, in order to produce good teacher performance and student achievement for schools in the coastal areas of the border island, it is necessary to have the leadership of the principal and teachers who have good social communication skills. The results showed that the principal's situational leadership had a significant effect on work motivation. Based on the research findings, it can be inferred that leadership style has a major role to develop work motivation and performance that have a positive impact on the quality of individuals in an organization.

This article discusses situational leadership practices from schools in various countries. Most articles focus on how situational leadership practices in schools. Based on the articles reviewed, there are various ways of collecting data related to situational leadership in schools; The most commonly used are questionnaires, interviews and observations.

Research on situational leadership practices in schools has been carried out in various countries. Table 2 shows that research on this theme has been carried out at various levels of education, both primary and secondary schools. Most research shows that situational leadership can improve teacher performance and can increase teacher commitment to the organization. The principal's situational leadership has a major role in developing work motivation and performance that has a positive impact on the quality of individuals in an organization (Mudiyantun, 2019)

The impact of applying situational leadership can improve school quality (Arisman & Prihatin, 2021). In addition, in the research conducted (Wanto, 2021), there is a positive relationship between situational leadership style and school climate on teacher integrity. Situational leadership practices need to be applied to strengthen the instructional and administrative duties of school principals, especially during times of global crisis (Pedroso et al., (2021), as well as the emergence of situational leadership during the COVID-19 pandemic called the new normal leadership (Francisco & Nuqui, 2020).

The general conclusion from studies of situational leadership practices in schools from various countries shows that the principal's leadership style is very important for an organization, especially educational institutions. Like other studies, this review also has limitations. First, the articles reviewed are only articles written in English, so there are still many studies from various countries that are not reviewed due to language limitations. Second, theses, dissertations and theses are not discussed in this article because they can cause publication bias. And finally, there is no single measure against which all studies can compare.

CONCLUSION

Principal leadership is very important for developing schools, because leaders can create positive change in education by encouraging staff to take initiative and change. The results of this literature review indicate that the principal's leadership style is very important for educational institutions. Situational leadership style is a situational leadership style that focuses on followers. From this point of view, to be effective, a school principal must be able to adapt his style to the demands of changing situations so that it can motivate teachers and can also affect knowledge/understanding for the teacher himself.

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